

DIRECTIONS D6.1:

Report on design choices for DC protection of Belgian energy hub

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Public Executive Summary

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Contributors: M. Van Deyck, A. Mohammadi, G. Chaffey, T. Roose and D. Van Hersem.

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This report presents the outcomes of the protection system design for the *Belgian Energy Hub*, as performed in Task 6.1: *Choice and specification of Belgian energy hub DC protection strategy*, and Task 6.2: *Design of DC protection and configuration for Belgian energy hub*. To this end, the methods developed in *Work Package 3 - Methodologies for designing protection of energy hubs* were used, in the phased methodology framework presented in *Deliverable 3.3 - Report on DC protection for energy hubs*.

In this deliverable, first, the outcomes of the system-level conceptual design are presented. It is shown that, given the relevant loss-of-infeed limits, at least one HVDC circuit breaker should be integrated in the electrical energy hub. Moreover, the ideal placement for this breaker is also found. Subsequently, a techno-economic analysis of the Belgian Energy Hub case study is performed to evaluate the potential of using preventive DC-side decoupling as an alternative protection concept to the selected partially selective system with one breaker per pole. This analysis showed that the operational cost increase caused by the preventive decoupling strategy is most severe if energy prices are high. Moreover, it was found that the use of this strategy in the Belgian Energy Hub would lead to many short periods of decoupling, thus requiring large numbers of coupling and decoupling operations.

Following this, the component-level detailed design is performed, using the outcomes of the system-level design phase as inputs, to dimension the key protection system components in the Belgian Energy Hub. Specifically, fault current limiting reactors are sized based on available ratings for converter overcurrent capacities and DC breaker operating times and current interruption capabilities. Depending on the considered breaker capabilities, converter parameters and DC grid operating conditions, the recommended DC reactor inductance ranges between 78 mH and 490 mH.

Together, the outcomes of the system-level conceptual design and the component-level detailed design form a comprehensive protection system that can be evaluated in detail in the last phase of the proposed protection system design methodology: *system-level performance evaluation*. This part will be further detailed in *Deliverable 6.2 - Report on time domain validation of DC protection for the Belgian energy hub*.

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